

A Thin-film, a-IGZO, 128b SRAM and LPRM Matrix with Integrated Periphery on Flexible Foil

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Abstract

A fast, 128 bit implementation of both SRAM and LPRM with integrated periphery in a thin-film a-IGZO technology is reported. The SRAM block can be read in 265 μ s/byte and written in 110 μ s/byte, consumes 12.3mW and has an area of 11.9mm². Furthermore, after power down an SRAM memory state retention time of 83s is shown. The LPRM can be read in 40 μ s/bit, consumes 4.50mW and has an area of 3.75mm². The SRAM enables fast volatile RAM memory for thin-film microprocessors, while the LPRM can be used to store the identification code for state-of-the-art thin-film RFID tags.

Index Terms

a-IGZO, Memory on Foil, Thin-Film Design, SRAM, Laser Programmable ROM

I. INTRODUCTION

After personal computing, the laptop and the smartphone, the internet of things is the next big wave in electronics. Billions of everyday objects will become smart, and need to be connected to the internet, paving the way for additional functionality [1]. However, to enable this, these devices need to have a sufficiently low price. These circuits might have sensors, actuators and communication to enable their revolutionary role. Using thin-film technology is a very promising route to fabricate high volume, low cost, low functionality circuits to integrate in these smart objects. Thin-film electronics can be manufactured on large areas, and is used today to create flat panel displays and sensitive plates for digital X-ray machines [2], [3]. Within the field on internet of things, the first major achievements with thin-film technologies have been shown, demonstrating direct smartphone readout of a flexible Near Field Communication (NFC) tag [4]. This circuit shows that thin-film electronics can provide sufficient speed

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for a range of low-end applications, at a price point which is significantly lower than what is possible using bulk silicon. In the future, these NFC tags will be equipped with sensors to monitor the environment, e.g. as a temperature patch for health monitoring. The data from the sensors needs to be processed and stored. To reduce the required transmission power, they need to first be compressed and stored locally, before they are transmitted in batch using the NFC protocol. This requires a local memory. In 2012, Myny *et al.* have shown a thin-film microprocessor, which was used for implementing a digital filter [5]. Still missing are the memory elements to store both the processor instructions and the data with high performance and low area footprint. It requires a non-volatile memory for storing the program instruction or identification code, and a random access memory as a working memory for the processor.

II. STATE OF THE ART

This paper shows the design and challenges of thin-film memories on foil. Although there is only little literature available, there are a few works that have already shown some first steps in this direction. With respect to non-volatile memories, Yang *et al.* showed a one-time programmable ROM array using anti-fuse capacitors in 2013 [6]. This work showed only 16 bits, with a footprint of 4.41mm^2 per bit. Nor the operating speed nor the peripherals have been reported. In 2014, Myny *et al.* showed a Print Programmable Read Only Memory (P²ROM), but it is slow compared to the processor (500Hz vs 2kHz) and has a high area footprint [7]. With respect to random access memories, only single memory cells have been shown, usually as a technology demonstrator for the thin-film technology. Previous digital systems [5], [7], [8] used registers to store single bytes, but no random access memory block was used. In 2011, Fukuda *et al.* showed an organic SRAM cell, but with a cell area of 21mm^2 , and a write speed of $1500\mu\text{s}$ [9]. In 2015, Geier *et al.* showed a single SRAM cell with very low power consumption, implemented in a complementary CNT technology, which is not yet a proven technology in production [10]. In 2016, finally, Avila-Niño *et al.* showed a matrix of 4×4 cells in an organic technology, but did not integrate periphery into the design [11].

[Fig. 1 about here.]

This paper shows a non-volatile memory and a fast accessible random access memory with high performance, low area consumption and low power. Area remains one of the most critical parameters for thin-film circuits to outperform silicon in terms of cost. Thin-film technology is inexpensive per unit area compared to traditional silicon, but this advantage can be offset by the increase in area. The smallest SRAM cell in thin-film technology shown today is 0.6mm^2 as presented by Geier *et al.* [10], compared to $0.027\mu\text{m}^2$ for the most recent 7nm CMOS technology [12]. For most envisioned applications, at least 1kb memory is needed. Assuming a cost of around $265\$/\text{m}^2$ [13], and a cost target of below $0.5\text{c}\$/\text{m}^2$, the area should be reduced by at least a factor 26.5, down to $0.023\text{mm}^2/\text{cell}$. In terms of ROM, the smallest cell shown is the P²ROM, using 0.09mm^2 . This means that the memory cells alone for a 1kbit memory would use 9mm^2 , more than doubling the size of a recent thin-film flexible NFC tag [14].

The second most critical parameter of these memories is speed. If these memories are combined with integrated microprocessors, the memory should not become the bottleneck. Previous works have either not shown data or

reported speeds of 650Hz and below. The thin-film microprocessor shown by Myny *et al.* in 2012 had a clock period of 2.1kHz or around 190 inverter stage delays. For the technology used in this work, the estimated operating frequency would be 1095Hz, and this should be the aim for the memory design [5]. In NFC tags corresponding to ISO15673, datarates of up to 6.62kb/s (fc/2048) or 26.48kb/s (fc/512) are required, imposing another spec on the speed.

III. TECHNOLOGY

This work uses a thin-film amorphous indium-gallium-zinc-oxide (a-IGZO) technology on flexible polyimide foil. The device stack is an etch stop layer (ESL) structure with critical dimension (CD) $5\mu\text{m}$ for SRAM or $3\mu\text{m}$ for LPROM, and a minimal channel length of $3 \times \text{CD}$, as shown in fig. 1. The device is comparable to the devices published by Chiang *et al.* [15] and Tripathi *et al.* [16]. Thin-film technology has a few key parameters which significantly impact design. Due to its unipolar nature, standard CMOS design techniques cannot be used. According to Myny *et al.* the best topology for thin-film design is a diode load topology with backgate [17], [18], but the noise margin remains limited, as shown by the transfer curves in fig. 2. Furthermore, mobility is limited to around $10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, a factor 50 to 100 lower than bulk Si. Due to long channel lengths and big overlap capacitors, the inverter stage delay for a $5\mu\text{m}$ technology is on average $4.78\mu\text{s}$, as displayed in fig. 3. Variability is also significant, with a standard deviation of $1.60\mu\text{s}$ for the inverter stage delay. These technological constraints will guide the further design. At this point, the gate oxide thickness is 200nm, in accordance to typical display processes [15], [16]. This requires a supply voltage of 15V, which can in an IoT context realistically be generated using a short distance communication link with the right antenna design. However, for circuits, our technology provider has a roadmap for scaling, reducing the oxide thickness as well as the critical dimension. This evolution can be seen in the work of Myny *et al.* between 2015 [18] and 2016 [14].

[Fig. 2 about here.]

[Fig. 3 about here.]

IV. SRAM DESIGN

A. SRAM cell design

[Fig. 4 about here.]

[Fig. 5 about here.]

[Fig. 6 about here.]

The single SRAM cell is shown in fig. 4. There is no good pull-up available in a-IGZO technology as only n-type devices can be used. This introduces new trade-offs compared to CMOS. The power consumption is dominated by the permanent on-current through one of the pull-ups. Additionally, a ratioed diode load inverter topology is used, requiring at least a 1:10 ratio for static stability, as shown in fig. 2. Making the load smaller (larger L) would

introduce lower power consumption but higher area use. Writability isn't a design challenge, because the ratioed logic automatically requires a weak pull-up and therefore easy writability. Fig. 4 details the optimal sizing selected as a tradeoff between speed, power consumption and area for the 5 μ m design rule, fig. 5 shows the layout. The measured static transfer curves for this SRAM cell are shown in fig. 6, as well as the dynamic read-write behavior, which is shown in fig. 7. The cell achieves a noise margin of 2.37V in read and 2.57V in hold at 15V supply. Furthermore, the measured speed of discharge is 0.361V/ms on a bitline with 1.08nF parasitic load due to the measurement setup, which translates to a 0.39 μ A discharge current. Finally, the measured static power consumption per cell is 54 μ W in hold. 128 cells together therefore consume 6.91mW, a significant portion of the total power consumption, as discussed later in Table I.

Thanks to thin-film a-IGZO technology's property of very low leakage [19], the cells will still keep their value on the internal node for a certain time after the supply is turned off, and can be regenerated when the supply is applied again. This effect depends on the I_{ds} current at $V_{gs}=0$, and is therefore dependent on the exact properties of the technology. Retention times between 10s and 83s have been measured in this technology, allowing for a significant reduction in power consumption when the memory is not used. The retention is fundamentally not limited to this value however, but dependent on the threshold voltage (V_T). V_T can be influenced by many technological parameters, like gate oxide thickness, semiconductor thickness, etc. Increasing V_T will have a positive effect on retention, however at the cost of speed.

[Fig. 7 about here.]

B. SRAM periphery

Fig. 8 shows the architecture of the 128bit SRAM block. All components (squares) are integrated on the foil, all timing and input signals (hexagons) are applied externally. Components include the 16x8 matrix core with SRAM cells, a 4-to-16 decoder, a precharge module, a bitline driver for write operations and a sense amplifier for cell readout.

[Fig. 8 about here.]

[Fig. 9 about here.]

The 4-to-16 decoder is shown in fig. 9 and is implemented with a standard single logic layer. NOR gates with high fan-in come with less penalty for unipolar diode load logic than for complementary logic, as no devices are put in series, comparable to dynamic circuits in CMOS. In this technology a decoder with up to 6 inputs is faster than the 2 logic layer equivalent and it consumes less power, as shown in fig. 9. Bigger arrays therefore benefit using the two layer implementation. The data on the bitlines can be detected in two ways. Either a regular inverter (see fig. 2) is used or a more complex sense amplifier (SA) can be selected. Both inverter and complex SA have been implemented. Fig. 10 shows the classical sense amplifier, with replacement of the p-type pull-ups by n-type pull-ups as is required using n-type only technology. Due to the substantial V_T variability in this technology, a large bitline swing is required to overcome the offset in the input pair of the sense amplifier, thereby limiting

the usefulness of the sense amplifier. In technologies with lower V_T variability (e.g. manufacturing lines vs lab environment) this disadvantage is reduced. Fig. 12 shows the measurement of one column of a 128b, SRAM matrix with sense amplifier. First, data is written in every cell. Then all the data is read out correctly. Fig. 11 shows the most optimal timing signals. The SRAM can be read at a rate of 265 μ s/byte and written at 110 μ s/byte without introducing bit errors, as shown in the timing diagram in fig. 11. If a sense amplifier is used, this slows down to 280 μ s/byte read rate, while the write speed stays 110 μ s/byte write rate. The performance decrease in this case is due to the extra stage delay introduced by the sense amplifier, which is relatively high compared to the gain thanks to the incomplete discharge of the bitline. Simulations show that for bitlines of 32 cells and more, using the described sense amplifier will significantly improve the performance of the system. The access speed of the memory is in the order of the present state-of-the-art thin-film microprocessor, showing clear promise for the memory. Fig. 13 shows the schmo plot for this device, and table I shows the power consumption.

[Fig. 10 about here.]

[Fig. 11 about here.]

[Fig. 12 about here.]

[Fig. 13 about here.]

V. LEPROM DESIGN

The architecture of the LEPROM is similar to the architecture of the SRAM omitting the write circuitry, and is shown in fig. 14. Furthermore, traditionally a programmable fixed pull-up is used in every line [7]. Since the main application for this memory today is coding flexible RFID tags, the output needs to be serialized so it can be transmitted directly. Therefore an 8-to-1 multiplexer is added. For full readout, a 7 bit digital counter can be connected as an address generator. The memory cells can be programmed using selective laser ablation, as exemplified in fig. 15. Similar to programming using ink-jet printing [7], selective laser ablation enables memory programming as a post-process, rather than at design level like in mask ROM. This allows us to make foils with different versions of software for a microprocessor or unique IDs for NFC tags. Resolution and throughput are critical for manufacturability, and depend on laser conditions and material stack, but are beyond the scope of this paper. In this work, laser spots down to 10 μ m x 10 μ m are used, which is a significant reduction in area compared to the printing implementation of Myny *et al.* [7]. In this work, it is proposed to use a precharge on every line instead of a fixed pull-up, as shown in fig. 16. Contrary to CMOS, there is no pMOS available to do this. An nMOS device is used, resulting in a V_T drop across the pull-up. The advantages are speed, area and power consumption. The cell area can now be reduced, because it is no longer required to keep the 1:10 ratio. This implies a smaller load for the wordline driver, which in turn can be made both faster and smaller. The size improvement can be seen on the individual cell level, as the cell size decreases from 4674 μ m² to 1440 μ m², but for our chips the size is the same since the same periphery layout was used. The speed is increased by using a precharge phase by the implementation of a larger precharge transistor compared to the original pull-up transistor, as is shown by the measurement of the

individual lines in fig. 17. Power is saved by eliminating a direct leakage path when both the pull-up and the pull-down are active together. The periphery blocks of the LEPROM are comparable to the SRAM design. To sense the bitline, an inverter is used, but in a faster design a sense amplifier (as demonstrated in the SRAM) can be used in the precharge LEPROM implementation. The measurement results of two rows of the chip are shown in fig. 18. The timing signals are applied externally, as specified by fig. 19. For the 3 μ m design rule, the maximum speed for the LEPROM with precharge is 25kHz, compared to 22.7kHz for the LEPROM without precharge transistors. Fig. 20 shows how the speed varies with supply voltage. Also the power consumption improves significantly, as shown in table I.

[Fig. 14 about here.]

[Fig. 15 about here.]

[Fig. 16 about here.]

[Fig. 17 about here.]

[Fig. 18 about here.]

[Fig. 19 about here.]

[Fig. 20 about here.]

VI. RESULTS

The fabricated chips are shown in figs. 21 and 22. Table II and III compare the presented chips to the state-of-the-art for respectively SRAM and ROM. The 128bit SRAM chip occupies 12.3mm², and has individual cells of 0.0276mm², a factor 21.7 improvement on the state-of-the-art. It can be written in 110 μ s/byte and read in 265 μ s, which is at least a factor 4 more than state-of-the-art. The power consumption is around 98.4 μ W/bit with periphery included, or 12.6mW in total. This is rather high compared to the total energy budget available in an NFC tag, and further research will need to focus on improving in this respect. The use of a sense amplifier is investigated, and it can be concluded that, though its effectiveness is likely smaller than for CMOS, it is still useful for larger arrays. With respect to LEPROM, this paper shows the clear advantage of using a precharge on the lines rather than a fixed pullup. The chip with pullup shows a 10% increase in speed, a 47% decrease in power consumption and a factor 3.25 decrease in area per memory unit. Compared to state-of-the-art, the proposed solution is 38x faster, requiring only 40 μ s to read a bit. Energywise, the system uses 35.1 μ W per bit, leaving significant room for improvement. Improvements in power consumption could be made by reducing the gate oxide thickness. The 128bit Laser Programmable ROM chips occupy 3.75mm², but can be significantly improved by a dedicated layout for a system with precharge. The individual cells are only 1440 μ m², a factor 63 improvement to current state-of-the-art.

[TABLE 1 about here.]

[TABLE 2 about here.]

[TABLE 3 about here.]

[Fig. 21 about here.]

[Fig. 22 about here.]

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the flexible thin-film SRAM and LPROM with integrated periphery exhibiting characteristics far beyond state-of-the-art are shown. A 128bit SRAM matrix with cells of only 0.028mm², is read out at 265μs/byte. Furthermore a 128bit LPROM readout is demonstrated, which is read out in just 40μs and 32.6x smaller compared to previous implementations thanks to the use of a precharge mechanism.

Further improvements in technology will significantly improve the performance of these circuits, mainly thanks to thinner gate dielectrics and smaller CDs. From the circuit perspective, this design could still be improved by adding timing circuits and expanding to larger array sizes.

This work shows for the first time that both SRAM and LPROM with integrated periphery can be fabricated in thin-film technology with low area and high speed, demonstrating the feasibility of integrating these components in an NFC tag.

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a)

b)

c)

Fig. 13. Schmoo plot for a) the readout of the SRAM matrix with Sense Amplifier, b) the readout of the SRAM matrix without Sense Amplifier, c) writing the SRAM matrix.

Fig. 14. Architecture of Laser Programmable ROM. Similar to the SRAM architecture without the writing part, but with a MUX to allow extracting the bits one by one as required for the RFID application.

Fig. 15. LPRM laserspot. Here, a spot size of $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ was used to disconnect a $10 \mu\text{m}$ track.

Fig. 16. Design of Laser Programmable ROM. This paper compares between traditional LPROM as in [7] and the LPROM with precharge. Adding precharge increases cell density and speed, and decreases power consumption.

Fig. 17. Measurement of the LPRM: single column readout with 16 cells. It shows the superior speed of the precharge concept, most clearly during the pull-up phase.

Fig. 18. Measurement of the LPRM: the readout of the first two rows of the matrix.

Fig. 19. Timing diagram for reading the LEPROM timing.

a)

b)

Fig. 20. Schmoo plot for a) the readout of the LPROM matrix without precharge. b) readout of the LPROM matrix with precharge.

Fig. 21. Die micrograph of the single SRAM cell and the SRAM matrix with precharge.

Fig. 22. Die micrograph of the LTPROM matrix without and with precharge.

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TABLE I
POWER CONSUMPTION OF THE CHIPS

	Power consumption [mW]
SRAM without SA, 128b	12.3
SRAM with SA, 128b	12.6
LPRM without precharge, 128b	8.60
LPRM with precharge,128b	4.50

TABLE II
COMPARISON TABLE FOR THIN-FILM SRAM DESIGNS

	SRAM with SA	SRAM without SA	Fukuda <i>et al.</i> , 2011 [9]	Geier <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [10]	Avila-Niño <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [11]
Technology / Lmin	a-IGZO / 15 μ m		Organic / 20 μ m	Compl. CNT	Organic / 50 μ m
Matrix size	16x8 bit		1 bit	1 bit	4x4 bit
Read time	280 μ s	265 μ s	Not available	Not available	Not available
Write time	110 μ s	110 μ s	1500 μ s	Not available	500 μ s
Unit size	200x138 μ m ²		5x4.2mm ²	1x0.6mm ²	> 1x1mm ²
Power per bit (incl. periphery)	98.4 μ W	96.3 μ W	Not available	10nW	Not available
Chip size	3.94x3.13mm ²	3.94x3.03mm ²	Not integrated	Not integrated	Not integrated

TABLE III
COMPARISON TABLE FOR THE THIN-FILM ROM DESIGNS

	LPROM with precharge	LPROM without precharge	Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [6]	Myny <i>et al.</i> , 2014 [7]
Technology / Lmin	a-IGZO / 9 μ m		Organic / 10 μ m	Hybrid compl. / 5 μ m
Matrix size	16x8 bit		4x4 bit	16x9 bit
Read time	40 μ s	44 μ s	Not available	1538 μ s
Unit Size	48x30 μ m ²	57x82 μ m ²	2.1x2.1mm ²	175x521 μ m ²
Power per bit (incl. periphery)	35.1 μ W	67.1 μ W	Not available	Not available
Chip size	1.5x2.5mm ²	1.5x2.5mm ²	Not integrated	8.97x6.93mm ²